

Running head: PEDIATRIC TBI AND SLEEP DISTURBANCE

**PEDIATRIC TRAUMATIC BRAIN INJURY AND ITS RELATION TO
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by

Alexander Fowler

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ABSTRACT

Sleep disturbance is one of the most frequently and earliest reported consequences of traumatic brain injury (TBI) (Bernard et al., 2017). The literature has identified myriad harmful correlates of sleep disturbance. For example, sleep disturbance appears to correlate positively with irritability, behavioral problems, emotional problems, executive functioning difficulties and learning difficulties, as well as inversely with academic performance (Beebe, 2006; Beebe et al., 2010; Danner & Phillips, 2008; Shay et al., 2014). This literature review aims to explore the genesis and the effects of sleep disturbance; specifically, to investigate the effects of TBI on sleep disturbance in humans injured before the age of 18 years. Analysis of those studies suggests that sleep behavior is compromised as a consequence of pediatric TBIs. Further assessment of the extant literature indicates that cognitive behavior therapy for insomnia (CBT-I) appears to be a promising intervention for mitigating the negative effects of sleep disturbance that arise from TBIs. As a result of this review, recommendations for clinical practice and suggestions for future research are discussed with the aim of improving the quality of life of this vulnerable population.

Statement of Original Work

I declare the following:

This systematic review of the literature represents this author's original findings. I acknowledge that where another author's words or ideas have been presented in this study, I have cited them in style.

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Name

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Date

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Introduction

Injuries of the human brain, including traumatic brain injury (TBI), can result in myriad neurological impairments (Agarwal et al., 2020). TBI is a major cause of injury-induced death across age groups (Bruns & Hauser, 2003; Popescu et al., 2015). TBI is the leading cause of death in people younger than 45 years old and it accounts for approximately 40% of total deaths caused by acute injury (Araki et al., 2017; Bruns & Hauser, 2003; Popescu et al., 2015). The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) estimated that the total mortality due to TBI in the United States of America (USA) was 17.8 per 100,000 in 2014 (Peterson et al., 2019). In the USA, TBI-induced death among hospitalized patients is estimated to be approximately six per 100,000 based on integrated historical national data while such deaths occurring outside of a hospital are estimated to occur in approximately 17 per 100,000 people (Bruns & Hauser, 2003; Popescu et al., 2015).

Sleep disturbance is among the most commonly reported symptoms of TBI, with some studies reporting incidence rates of up to 87% during the acute phase, i.e., <72 hours post-injury (Bernard et al., 2017). Cormier (1990) conceptualized sleep disturbance as encompassing "...disorders of initiating and maintaining sleep (DIMS, insomnias), disorders of excessive somnolence (DOES), disorders of sleep–wake schedule, and dysfunctions associated with sleep, sleep stages, or partial arousals (parasomnias)" (p. 398). Frequently reported sleep disturbances following a pediatric TBI include bedtime resistance, fatigue, sleep breathing difficulties, difficulty initiating and maintaining sleep, sleep efficiency, sleep latency, hypersomnolence, parasomnias, decreased/increased sleep duration as well as greater overall sleep disturbance (e.g., Bogdanov et al., 2018; Botchway et al., 2019b; Fischer et al., 2018; Shay et al., 2014; Sumpter et al., 2013). Such sleep disturbance in children has been found to affect behavior as

well as cognitive and emotional functioning (Fischer et al., 2018; Lalonde et al., 2020; Shay et al., 2014; Tham et al., 2012). Remarkably, in contrast to the adult literature, there is a paucity of research on sleep disturbance in children. However, the research which does exist suggests that children with TBI experience greater sleep difficulties relative to baseline and control data which included typically developing children, siblings, those with orthopedic injury, and suffers of non-cranial/superficial bodily injury (Bernard et al., 2017; Bogdanov et al., 2018; Fischer et al., 2018; Milroy et al., 2008; Shay et al., 2014; Sumpter et al., 2013; Tham et al., 2012).

In this document, sleep data following a pediatric TBI are examined. Based on the adult literature, it was hypothesized that children who experienced a TBI would be more likely to report sleep disturbances than siblings; healthy controls; or children with an extracranial, orthopedic, or minor bodily injury. This review also examines the time course of post-injury sleep concerns, severity-specific sequelae, risk factors, and possible interventions, although no specific hypotheses were posited for these points of investigation.

Method

Literature Search

Publications were identified using PsycInfo, and EBSCO Academic Search Premiere. The search terms used were “*pediatric traumatic brain injury*” AND “*sleep disturbance*”, as well as “*pediatric traumatic brain injury*” AND “*sleep.*” A filter was placed on the search so as to include only studies published between January 01, 2000 and December 29, 2020. A search of the databases found 113 total results in EBSCO Academic Search Premiere, and 62 results in PsycINFO for a total of 175 references.

Study Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Studies were excluded from the review if they were duplicates, meta-analytic reviews, or case studies; if the range of age at injury for participants was not specified; if the publication was not in a scholarly journal; or if the study was published after September 30, 2020. Publications were included in the review if they were peer-reviewed and published in English after the year 2000 with or without a control group. They were also included if a group of participants suffered from one or more TBIs exclusively before the age of 18 years and post-TBI sleep disturbance were specifically evaluated. Applying these criteria, a total of 23 publications were selected. Seventeen additional publications that were not identified during the initial search were included in the review to provide contextual information with the aim of appropriately framing the findings resulting in 40 total articles (Agarwal et al., 2020; Araki et al., 2017; Beebe, 2006; Beebe et al., 2010; Bruns & Hauser, 2003; Cormier, 1990; Danner & Phillips, 2008; Dewan et al., 2018; Gómez-de-Regil et al., 2019; Hawley, 2003; Meltzer et al., 2012; Ouellet et al., 2004; Peterson et al., 2019; Popescu et al., 2015; Sadeh, 2011; Sambuco et al., 2008; Schneier et al., 2006).

Review of the Literature

Description of the Child Sample

There was great variability among the age of participants within the 23 studies identified. All of the studies included at least one group of pediatric participants who were younger than 18. A total sample size of 4494 (56% male) was calculated among the 23 studies identified. The sample population age range was zero to 17.9 years. The number of participants in the studies varied widely with a range of five to 926. A large majority of the studies reviewed (83%) included a total sample size of 50 or greater, and more than half of the studies (57%) included a

total sample size of 100 or more. Eighteen of the 23 studies reviewed (78%) were longitudinal studies; 10 of the 23 (43%) conducted an intra-severity assessment of sleep disturbance. The sample was populated by international participants who hailed from the USA, the United Kingdom, Canada, the Republic of Lithuania, and the Commonwealth of Australia. Eighteen of the studies (78%) employed a control group, 11 of those studies used an orthopedic injury (OI), extracranial injury, minor bodily injury or trauma control group. Five studies utilized a typically developing control sample, one incorporated siblings, and one employed previously published data sets for comparison data. Notably, a number of the articles reviewed included participants with pre-existing deficits, including pre-injury learning difficulties, and internalizing problems.

The present literature review incorporated numerous studies that utilized diverse samples (e.g., Crichton et al., 2018a; Tham et al., 2012). Suskauer and colleagues (2018) utilized a sample in which 54% of the total participants were White (36% were Black) whilst Fischer and co-researchers (2018) studied a TBI sample which was 31% Caucasian. This is important to note as the incorporation of ethnically and racially diverse samples in research may allow for sound practical application. A number of the studies reviewed did not provide detailed data on participant race or ethnicity (e.g., Bernard et al., 2020; Bogdanov et al., 2018; Botchway et al., 2019a & 2019b; Corti et al., 2019; Iyer et al., 2019; Lah et al., 2019). Other studies did not clearly delineate race or ethnicity. For example, Shay and colleagues (2014) presented only the number and percentage of “nonwhite race” participants without operationalizing the transitional variable of “nonwhite race.” Similarly, Lalonde and co-researchers (2020) only provided detailed demographic data relating to the TBI group not the control group. Curiously, Crichton and colleagues (2018a) performed an attrition analysis and found that the participants who completed a secondary assessment were more White and less diverse than the original sample ($p=.001$).

Specifically, they reported that White participants accounted for about 67% of their initial sample, but, at follow-up, White individuals accounted for 77% of the sample. They also reported that the sample was marginally more male at follow-up ($p=.15$). Relatedly, Botchway and colleagues (2019a & 2019b) reported a substantially higher rate of attrition in the TBI groups for males (relative to females) at a 20-year follow-up ($p<.05$). This difference was not found in the typically developing control group. Whilst other reviewed studies did not conduct such attrition analyses, these results may presage disparate attrition rates across the studies analyzed at present.

Prevalence of TBI and Related Sleep Disturbance

Numerous international studies have identified TBI as the leading cause of disability and death in children and adolescents (e.g., Araki et al., 2017; Popescu et al., 2015). During 2014, within the USA, the leading cause of TBIs in children were falls according to the CDC (Peterson et al., 2019). The annual incidence of TBI is substantial; for example, in the year 2000, the estimated incidence for children in the USA was approximately 70 per 100,000 based on hospitalization data (Schneider et al., 2006). In 2014, there were nearly 2.9 million hospitalizations, emergency department visits, and deaths associated with TBI, which included more than 837,000 children (Peterson et al., 2019). Similar global incidence rates were found in the international literature, but incidence varies across countries, with the highest rates reported across North America and Europe (Dewan et al., 2018). Such variance in incidence among global regions may be due to actual discrepancies in occurrence or may reflect differences in the surveillance thereof.

The incidence of sleep disturbance following a TBI in pediatric patients is high. Bernard and associates (2017) identified incidence of approximately 87% among children during the

acute phase (<72 hours post-injury). Similarly, Ouellet and colleagues (2004) performed a systematic review of the literature and estimated that 30-70% of individuals of all ages evidence sleep disturbance after a TBI. Research indicates that a pediatric TBI may be associated with a heightened risk of sleep disturbance relative to a TBI in an adult. For instance, Corti and co-researchers (2019) found that children under 17 who had a TBI were significantly less likely to awaken feeling refreshed relative to adults (18+) with comparable injuries, despite the fact that the under 17 children were sleeping for significantly longer periods than the 18+ group.

Sleep Impacts

The extant literature indicates that pediatric TBI is associated with an increased risk of subsequent sleep disturbances, including, for example, difficulties initiating/maintaining sleep, decreased/increased sleep duration, sleep breathing difficulties, diminished sleep efficiency, prolonged sleep latency, parasomnias, bedtime resistance, fatigue, and greater overall sleep disturbance (Bogdanov et al., 2018; Botchway et al., 2019b; Fischer et al., 2018; Shay et al., 2014; Sumpter et al., 2013). Children with a TBI more frequently experience sleep disturbances relative to control groups, as assessed by measures including, but not limited to, actigraphy, the Sleep Disturbances Scale for Children (SDSC), the Sleep Self-Report (SSR) Questionnaire, the Children's Sleep Habits Questionnaire (CSHQ), and a 28-item post-concussive symptoms scale (e.g., Fischer et al., 2018; Milroy et al., 2008; Shay et al., 2014; Sumpter et al., 2013; Tham et al., 2012).

Post-TBI sleep disturbance also appears to be persistent in some patients. In 2012, Tham and colleagues published a longitudinal study with a large sample ($N=926$). They reported that, following a TBI, children 2-17 years old experience persistent sleep disturbances at 12 months, notwithstanding severity, and up to 24 months following a moderate or severe TBI. These

researchers further indicated that sleep disturbances may actually increase, not decline, in the first 12 months post-TBI. Interestingly, Bogdanov and colleagues (2018) conducted a study and found that there were no significant correlations between time since injury and various sleep disturbances (i.e., total SDSC score, initiating and maintaining sleep, excessive somnolence, and sleep breathing difficulties). This contradicts the bulk of the literature which has identified this association (e.g., Bernard et al., 2020; Bernard et al., 2017). Fischer and co-researchers (2018) reported that the Glasgow Coma Scale injury severity score was positively associated with child-reported fatigue at a 12-month follow-up, but it was not associated with child-reported fatigue at six months. Such findings serve to underscore the complex relationship between injury severity, time since injury, and sleep disturbance following a TBI in a pediatric population. Nevertheless, the existing research clearly demonstrates that pediatric TBIs appear to be associated with subsequent sleep disturbances generally, but the nature and qualities thereof remain a burgeoning field of inconclusive investigation. Shay and colleagues (2014), for example, found that post-pediatric-TBI sleep difficulties include more parasomnias and significantly more bedtime resistance at a six-month follow-up as well as shorter sleep duration in children with TBI versus children with OI at six- and 12-month follow-ups.

Shay and colleagues (2014) also investigated severity-specific sequelae following pediatric TBI. They found that pediatric patients diagnosed with severe TBI had significantly greater bedtime resistance at a six-month follow-up assessment and significantly shorter sleep duration than those diagnosed with a mild or moderate TBI. These findings rampart much of the established literature. Likewise, Beebe and associates (2007) found that sleep disturbance persisted in children with severe (but not moderate) TBI over 48 months post-injury relative to an OI control group. Importantly, these researchers cautioned that the moderate TBI group had a

greater level of reported sleep disturbance pre-injury relative to the OI ($p=.02$) and severe TBI ($p=.04$) groups. This discrepancy may have confounded the results, contributing to the finding that children diagnosed with a moderate TBI did not evidence post-injury sleep disturbances relative to an OI control group. Crichton and co-researchers (2018b) reported that fatigue prevalence consequent to a pediatric TBI was 27% in those diagnosed with moderate/severe TBI and 10% in those diagnosed with a mild TBI six-months post-injury. This reflected a 27% and 8% increase, respectively as compared to pre-injury incidence. These researchers also reported a 5% increase in overall sleep disturbance among children with mild TBI from pre-injury to a six-month follow-up, but the increase in prevalence among the moderate/severe TBI group was three times greater (15%). Similarly, Bogdanov and collaborators (2018) reported that children, 5-15 years old, with severe but not moderate TBI, were more likely to evidence increased disturbances in initiating and maintaining sleep as indicated by the SDSC, relative to an OI control group. Crichton and co-researchers (2018a) reported that both a pediatric mild TBI group and a pediatric moderate/severe TBI group evidenced worsened fatigue scores at 12-month follow-up (including sleep/rest fatigue, cognitive fatigue, general fatigue, and total fatigue) relative to the scores of controls. These results are supported by findings from Landry-Roy and colleagues (2017), who indicated that preschool children, aged 18-60 months, experienced marginally increased sleep difficulties relative to OI and typically developing child control groups following a mild TBI. Further, Bernard and co-researchers (2020 & 2017) reported that, relative to a control group, mild TBI predicted sleep disturbance symptoms up to a three-month follow-up but not at an eight-month follow-up. These conclusions are buttressed by the findings of Botchway and co-researchers (2019b) who reported that, at a 20-year follow-up, those with moderate and severe TBI evidenced significantly more sleep disturbance than those with a diagnosis of mild

TBI ($p=.029$). Taken together, these findings suggest that children with TBIs of greater severity are at an increased risk of experiencing sleep difficulties that are more disturbing and persistent relative to children with a TBI of lesser severity.

Contrary to previous literature, Bogdanov and colleagues (2018) found that parents of children with moderate TBI, but not severe TBI, reported that their children experienced greater levels of overall sleep disturbances, excessive somnolence, and sleep breathing difficulties following the injury as compared to an OI control group. The authors cautioned that the reported intra-severity discrepancy may be related to methodological issues, including significant differences between groups in time since injury ($p<.001$), age at injury ($p<.001$), and the differing degrees of care that children with moderate and severe TBI receive (Bogdanov et al., 2018). Furthermore, Bogdanov and associates reported that the moderate and severe groups only differed significantly in comparison to a control group; relative to one another, the groups differed only marginally on each of the sleep outcomes measured. The relationships between TBI severity, sleep disturbances, and outcomes are undoubtedly complex, but the increased incidence of sleep disturbance following a pediatric TBI, irrespective of severity, is well-established.

Although post-TBI sleep disturbance in children tends to peak during the acute phase post-injury, continued investigation by contemporary researchers has found that post-pediatric-TBI sleep disturbance may persist into adulthood for some individuals (e.g., Bernard et al., 2017; Botchway et al., 2019a). Botchway and co-researchers (2019b) conducted a 20-year follow-up study among patients who were zero to 12 years old at the time of the injury to investigate the long-term consequences on sleep following a TBI in a pediatric population. They reported that patients with severe or moderate TBI evidenced significantly greater total sleep duration as compared to those with a mild TBI 20 years later but that the combined TBI group differed only

marginally and non-significantly from healthy controls. Previous research conducted by Botchway and fellows (2019a) found that relative to a control group, at a 20-year follow-up, patients with TBI, notwithstanding severity, reported a trend toward poorer sleep quality ($p=.054$) with an increased risk in patients diagnosed with a moderate TBI relative to a severe TBI ($p=.015$). Such research signifies that post-TBI sleep disturbance follows a complex and dynamic pattern over long periods of time and across individuals. Sleep disturbance is correlated with pediatric TBI but the manifestation of sleep disturbance following such injury appears to be further associated with certain risk factors, beyond severity, which will be delineated in subsequent sections. If such risk factors are present, then long-term, intermittent assessment of sleep disturbance should be conducted concomitantly with appropriate intervention.

Academic, Social, and Psychological Impacts

The literature reviewed suggests that sleep disturbances in children following a TBI significantly and independently raise the risk of poor cognitive outcomes over time. For example, Crichton and researchers (2018a) reported that cognitive fatigue worsens significantly over time (up to 12 months post-TBI) in children one to 16 years old. Shay and colleagues (2014) found that sleep disturbances in pediatric patients with severe TBI was associated with decreased cognitive functioning, as measured by the Shape School Task at six- and 12-month follow-ups. Crichton and fellows (2018b) reported that children with moderate/severe TBI were significantly more likely to develop symptoms of inattention at six-month follow-up relative to children with a mild TBI ($p<.05$). Importantly, Howell and co-researchers (2019) found that such cognitive symptoms are independently associated with prolonged recovery time in children 7-12 years old. However, prior research by Howell and colleagues (2016) evidenced only a marginal association in a slightly older sample of children when investigating the same variables. Notably,

Howell and colleagues (2019 & 2016) indicated that sleep disturbance is, in its own regard, not associated with prolonged post-concussive symptom duration in children (7-12 years) or adolescents (13-18 years). This is surprising, given the state of the literature which generally espouses a connection between sleep disturbance and consequent symptom manifestation (e.g., Shay et al., 2014). Such findings serve to underscore the various dynamics involved in post-TBI symptom formation.

Post-pediatric-TBI sleep disturbance has been found to be associated with behavioral and emotional consequences, including internalizing problems, externalizing problems, and executive functioning impairments, as measured by the Behavioral Rating Inventory of Executive Functioning (BRIEF) and the Child Behavior Checklist (CBCL) (Shay et al., 2014). Fischer and researchers (2018) similarly reported that post-TBI sleep disturbance in children was associated with both externalizing and internalizing behavior problems as well as fatigue. Lalonde and colleagues (2020) reported that post-TBI sleep disturbance and post-concussive symptoms generally are significant and independent predictors of lower quality parent-child interactions at a six-month follow-up. Furthermore, research conducted by Tham and co-researchers (2012) found that sleep disturbances are predictive of poorer functional outcomes (e.g., worse self-care, poorer communication, decreased activity participation) in children 2-17 years old who have sustained a moderate or severe TBI. This suggests that post-TBI sleep disturbances in children may contribute to academic, social, and psychiatric difficulties. Such findings also serve to highlight the potential social and academic ramifications of post-pediatric-TBI sleep disturbance.

Previously reviewed literature, for example, Bogdanov and fellows (2018), Crichton and co-researchers (2018a), and Shay and associates (2014) demonstrated that excessive somnolence,

cognitive fatigue, bedtime resistance, and parasomnias are associated with TBI in children. Such factors, among others, are likely to be independently related to a number of negative outcomes across academic and social settings, as sleep disturbance appears to maintain a positive relationship with irritability, behavioral problems, emotional problems, learning difficulties, and executive function impairments, as well as a negative association with academic performance (e.g., Beebe, 2006; Beebe et al., 2010; Danner & Phillips, 2008; Shay et al., 2014). Post-pediatric-TBI treatment often fails to incorporate interventions to assess or to improve social and academic functioning despite clear indications from the available literature that such interventions may be valuable in mitigating the short- and long-term consequences of pediatric TBIs. This matter is especially disconcerting, given that TBIs in school-age children may impede subsequent age-appropriate social and academic development and, consequently, long-term outcomes.

Brain Functioning Impacts

Shay and colleagues (2014) reported that general sleep functioning has not been shown to relate to poorer neuropsychological test performance following a pediatric TBI. Nevertheless, pediatric TBIs appear to affect brain functioning. Nacajauskaite and fellows (2006) reported that the presence of sleep disturbance is a significant predictor of parent concern of the child's having brain damage. Relatedly, in a relatively large sample of children ($N=110$) who were recently diagnosed with a mild TBI, there was a statistically significant negative association between sleep disturbance (including fatigue) and gray matter volume as well as connectivity within two nodes of the default mode network (DMN), the posterior cingulate cortex and the medial prefrontal cortex (Iyer et al., 2019). These researchers reported that decreased functional connectivity within these two key nodes of the DMN was also associated with elevated scores on

a composite index of sleep disturbance. They demonstrated high predictive power (AUC=0.86) when basing predictions for clinical outcomes on structural and functional measures of the posterior cingulate cortex and medial prefrontal cortex, specifically by means of assessment with MRI and voxel-based morphometry with machine learning. This suggests that functional-structure profiles of core default mode regions, specifically, and assessment of brain functioning, generally, harbors valuable diagnostic and prognostic information in clinical settings. The utilization of this combination of structural and functional brain indices with machine learning appears to outperform the relatively routine EEG examination in predicting relevant clinical outcomes following a TBI in pediatric settings. Korinthenberg and collaborators (2004), for example, reported that EEG results observed immediately and at a four- to six-week follow-up did not correlate with sleep disturbances in children three to 13 years old following a minor head injury. Such findings highlight the value in utilizing nascent, evidence-based assessments across clinical settings.

Risk Factors

When making a determination of recommendations for clinical intervention following a TBI, the consideration of risk factors is of great importance in guiding such decisions. Research aimed at identifying risk factors for sleep disturbances consequent to a pediatric TBI is limited. The literature reviewed at present indicates the following as correlates of post-TBI sleep disturbances:

- Alteration of consciousness at acute injury phase (Landry-Roy et al., 2017)
- Elevated parental stress (Landry-Roy et al., 2017)
- Female sex (Botchway et al., 2019b; Tham et al., 2012)

- Injury severity (Beebe et al., 2007; Bogdanov et al., 2018; Botchway et al., 2019a; Botchway et al., 2019b; Crichton et al., 2018a; Fischer et al., 2018; Shay et al., 2014; Tham et al., 2012)
- Lower parental marital satisfaction (Landry-Roy et al., 2017)
- Older age at time of injury (Crichton et al., 2018a & 2018b)
- Parental educational attainment (Bernard et al., 2020)
- Poorer family functioning (Landry-Roy et al., 2017)
- Post-TBI psychological symptoms (Beebe et al., 2007; Botchway et al., 2019a; Crichton et al., 2018b; Fischer et al., 2018; Provance et al., 2020; Tham et al., 2012)
- Post-TBI physical/motor symptoms (Crichton et al., 2018b)
- Pre-injury psychological symptoms (Crichton et al., 2018b; Provance et al., 2020)
- Pre-injury sleep disturbance/fatigue (Crichton et al., 2018b; Landry-Roy et al., 2017)
- Younger age at time of injury (Bogdanov et al., 2018)

Howell and co-researchers (2019) reported that being female was only marginally associated ($p=.07$) with increased sleep disturbance post-TBI across age groups, but being female was significantly associated with increased somatic symptomatology, which was found to be independently associated with prolonged symptom duration. This is remarkable because 100% of children in the acute injury phase (<72 hours post-TBI) reported somatic symptoms (87% had sleep disturbance) while only 20% of the trauma control group evidenced somatic symptoms and just 18% evidenced sleep disturbance (Bernard et al., 2017). Such findings may indicate an indirect correlation between female sex and post-TBI sleep disturbance with somatic

symptomatology serving to bridge the two variables. Landry-Roy and co-researchers (2017) also reported that there was no significant difference in identified post-TBI sleep disturbance among a significantly younger sample (aged 18-60 months) between males and females (nighttime sleep duration as measured by actigraphy; $p=0.31$). They speculated that the cause of the discrepancy between published studies may be due to the fact that "...mechanisms affecting sleep (post-TBI) differ with developmental stage" (p. 21). This suggests that the manifestation of post-TBI sleep disturbance is modified by numerous factors that may change with age. This is supported by research by Beebe and associates (2007) as well as Botchway and colleagues (2019a) who reported that there was no significant association between gender/sex and sleep disturbance over 48-months and at a 20-year follow-up, respectively. Such findings underscore the intricate and equivocal sequelae of TBI among pediatric patients, which is complicated by the fact that many publications utilize relatively small sample sizes. Furthermore, members of different genders may present with differences in symptom reporting, further confounding interpretation of the extant literature and complicating the derivation of appropriate clinical recommendations therefrom. As beforementioned, Howell and co-researchers (2019) found that sex seems to modify symptom-reporting behavior. Nevertheless, the question remains as to whether such differences between males and females are definite or if they are wholly the result of differences in reporting between groups.

The extant research is conflicting in the determination of the relationship between age and post-TBI sleep disturbance. Bogdanov and colleagues (2018) indicated that younger age at the time of injury was correlated with greater post-TBI sleep disturbance. Seemingly contradictory results were reported by Crichton and collaborators (2018a & 2018b). They reported significant positive associations between age and levels of fatigue 12 months post-

injury. Attaining a representative understanding of the data is further obfuscated by the fact that, across age groups, initial symptom presentation following a TBI does not seem to differ for the first seven days post-injury, indicating that the aforementioned differences between age and symptom severity may change over time (Corti et al., 2019). Importantly, Howell and fellows (2019) found that symptom-reporting behavior appears to be similar between children and adolescents within the first 21 days following a mild-TBI. Therefore, these results, when juxtaposed on the research conducted by Bogdanov and colleagues (2018) and Crichton and co-researchers (2018a), suggest that the aforementioned age group differences appear to manifest over longer durations and may not be apparent within 21 days post-injury. Further, Botchway and collaborators (2019a & 2019b) did not identify a significant correlation between age at injury and post-TBI sleep disturbance at a 20-year follow-up. These findings may serve to portend the attenuation of this association over long periods of time (e.g., 20 years). The nature of such associations suggests that factors not yet subjected to investigation may mediate these relationships. Interestingly, Beebe and associates (2007) reported that age at injury was not associated with sleep over time (48 months), but their analysis contrasted only retrospective baseline data with combined post-TBI follow-up data, potentially moderating those results. These seemingly contradictory findings are not necessarily mutually exclusive. Rather, they may signify that the relationship between age at injury and risk of sleep disturbance is a highly dynamic one, but further research is needed in this regard.

The presence of certain comorbid conditions also appears to have some association with an increased risk for sleep disturbance subsequent to a TBI in children and adolescents. For example, Botchway and fellows (2019a) reviewed long-term symptom persistence following a pediatric TBI in children who were between zero and 12 years old at the time of the incident.

They found that sleep disturbances were associated with anxiety and pain, the latter of which was independently associated with higher risk of insomnia and excessive daytime sleepiness 20 years later. This is supported by research that was conducted by Provance and co-researchers (2020) and Tham and associates (2012) which reported that children who experienced pain post-TBI were at greater risk of experiencing sleep disturbance than those who did not. Fischer and co-researchers (2018) found that such pain was significantly associated with sleep disturbance at a six-month follow-up but not at 12 months. A similar finding was published by Crichton and associates (2018b). They reported only a marginal association between pain (assessed at six months) and fatigue (assessed at 12 months). Botchway and fellows (2019b) reported that anxiety and pain were not significantly associated with sleep disturbance 20 years post-injury, but this finding may be associated with the smaller sample size utilized in this study compared with the research by Botchway and colleagues (2019a). These findings suggest that post-TBI pain is likely associated with sleep disturbance in children but the qualities of this relationship over time are less clear.

Crichton and colleagues (2018b) conducted research assessing differing domains of fatigue in children post-TBI, including cognitive fatigue, sleep/rest fatigue, and general fatigue. They reported that “preinjury fatigue and psychological functioning identified those at greatest risk of fatigue 12 months post-TBI” (p. 224). Their findings also indicated that the different fatigue typologies assessed at 12 months were often predicted by different variables at six months (e.g., pre-/post-injury emotional functioning, pre-injury fatigue, post-injury motor functioning). Although these predictors fluctuated among fatigue domains, predictors “consistently included physical/motor function as well as sleep and mood symptoms postinjury” (p. 224). Similar findings have been reported by other researchers. For example, Bogdanov and

associates (2018) found that the different types of sleep disturbance appear to be associated with distinct variables. These findings serve to underscore the importance of monitoring patients and of exploring variables that correlate with post-TBI sleep disturbance generally as well as the myriad domains thereof over time to ensure that no unaddressed residual or related symptomatology persists or emerges subsequent to the initial clinical evaluation.

Review of Interventions/Assessments

Despite the common use of the CBCL as a measure for sleep disturbance throughout the studies identified, it is recommended that a review assessing the validity of the CBCL in a post-pediatric-TBI sample be promptly conducted, as research undertaken by Landry-Roy and associates (2017) found that the actigraphy results of their study did not correlate with CBCL sleep scale scores. This suggests that these measures may assess distinct features of sleep. This problem may be avoided through the utilization of a battery of assessments from multiple sources. Sumpter and co-researchers (2013), for example, used actigraphy as well as parent- and child-report measures, namely, the CSHQ and SSR, respectively. Sumpter and colleagues (2013) wrote, “Children themselves may not associate sleep disturbance with daytime problems or may be unable to articulate problems” (p. 832). They also cited previous research (e.g., Hawley, 2003) which found that family members may also underreport sleep difficulties in patients due to a heightened attention to physical and behavioral changes after a TBI.

Since different assessments may evaluate different domains or features of sleep disturbance, the consequent research should aim to uncover the appropriate use of the respective measures so as to provide researchers and practitioners alike the most accurate understanding as to the nature of the data being analyzed. Such research will contribute to addressing discrepancies in the findings of the presently reviewed literature while concomitantly providing

practitioners with more-precise information regarding assessment results beyond that which is available at present. The research reviewed also conveyed concern surrounding the utilization of other assessments, such as actigraphy, in clinical settings. Sumpter and associates (2013), for example, wrote, “However, actigraphy is only a behavioral correlate of sleep and limitations include variability of devices, high sensitivity to sleep but low specificity to wake (resulting in potential underestimation of WASO [Wake after Sleep Onset]), and a lack of validity studies across specific pediatric age groups and clinical populations (Meltzer et al., 2012; Sadeh, 2011)” (p. 833).

The data derived from this review suggest that the incorporation of parent report in tandem with validated and objective measures of post-TBI symptomatology is prudent. Suskauer and co-researchers (2018) found that parents identified post-injury sleep disturbance not captured by the Acute Concussion Evaluation (ACE). Nevertheless, the utilization of parent report should be done solely in conjunction with other assessments of sleep disturbance, as parents and caregivers may inaccurately report sleep disturbances, and the respective measures employed may fail to detect relevant post-concussive sleep disturbance. For example, Milroy and colleagues (2008) found that parents and caregivers reported sleep disturbances in their children which were not indicated by child report or by objective measures such as actigraphy post-TBI. Hence, a battery of assessments should be utilized throughout treatment and follow-up, or perhaps future researchers will develop a single, valid, appropriate assessment to incorporate into institutional neuroradiological protocols as well as clinical settings generally. Importantly, Howell and co-researchers (2019 & 2016) reported that the association between individual symptom profiles and the time to resolution of post-TBI symptoms varies by age, with significant differences evidenced between children and adolescents. Such findings suggest that

although global symptom ratings are advantageous in one's formulation of appropriate clinical treatment, domain- and age-specific assessments may serve as more effective means by which clinicians can accomplish this objective.

Iyer and co-researchers (2019) reported that decreased functional connectivity in two key nodes within the DMN was associated with elevated scores on a measure of sleep disturbance within a pediatric sample. They demonstrated strong predictive power when basing predictions for clinical outcomes on functional and structural brain measures assessed using MRI and voxel-based morphometry with machine learning. The incorporation of this combination of structural and functional brain indices with machine learning appears promising, as it seems to surpass the commonly prescribed EEG examination in predicting relevant clinical outcomes following a pediatric TBI. For example, Korinthenberg and collaborators (2004) reported that EEG results observed at the acute-injury phase and at a follow-up four to six weeks later did not correlate with sleep disturbances in children three to 13 years old following a slight head injury. These findings reinforce the apparent value of employing novel evidence-based assessments across pediatric TBI protocols in clinical settings.

Although a number of post-pediatric-TBI interventions have been proposed, research related to such interventions appears limited, as few studies detailing interventions were identified in this review. Cognitive behavior therapy (CBT) is the most common intervention following a TBI in children (Gómez-de-Regil et al., 2019). Nevertheless, the intervention often does not directly address sleep disturbances. The successful treatment of sleep difficulties following a TBI will likely lead to clinically significant improvements in the pediatric patient's daily functioning across domains. For example, Shay and colleagues (2014) found that post-TBI sleep difficulties predicted greater behavioral and emotional problems as well as decreased social

functioning and everyday executive functioning based on parent report. These results suggest that sleep disturbances may spark or stoke problems in day-to-day functioning in children following a TBI and that the evaluation of children with a TBI should, at a minimum, include screening questions about sleep disturbance.

Lah and collaborators (2019) assessed the acceptability of a specially formulated CBT derivative known as cognitive behavioral therapy for insomnia (CBT-I) in adolescents (aged 11-13 years) following a TBI. The researchers observed clinically significant improvements in insomnia symptomatology in a majority of cases (75%), and fatigue in all cases following four weeks of manualized CBT-I delivered individually. This research provides evidence indicating that CBT-I is a viable treatment for insomnia and fatigue in adolescents following a TBI. Notably, there was little published research on interventions to improve sleep disturbance in children following a TBI among the databases reviewed, as only one such study was identified.

Discussion

Conclusions

The present review of the literature has identified a consistent association between TBI and consequent sleep disturbance affirming the hypothesis posited. This review further supports the researchers who predicted that post-TBI sleep disturbance may persist for 12 months or more. Numerous correlates of post-TBI sleep disturbance in a pediatric population were identified. The most commonly reported associations of such sleep disturbance included injury severity, post-TBI psychological symptoms, and pre-injury sleep disturbance. The nature and clinical significance of other correlates of post-TBI sleep disturbance in children (e.g., female sex and age at injury) were more ambiguous, as research suggests a complex relationship between each of these variables and sleep disturbance post-injury. Children who experience post-TBI sleep disturbance appear to have an elevated risk of developing daytime impairments across

academic, social, and psychological functioning. Poorer functioning across these spheres may prove to have a chilling effect on child and adolescent development. The sleep disturbance treatment and assessment methods reviewed support the utility of a focused assessment battery post-TBI and the inclusion of long-term follow-up assessments, particularly in individuals presenting with certain risk factors. In both cases, CBT-I is indicated as a treatment for post-TBI sleep disturbance.

Recommendations for Clinical Practice

Sleep disturbances after TBI are reported in up to 87% of children (Bernard et al., 2017). Given the high risk of negative outcomes associated with sleep disturbances, practitioners should conduct long-term follow-up to attend to any relevant developments, and to identify and employ clinical interventions as needed. It is recommended that such interventions include both the pediatric patient and his or her family as the family unit may serve to assist in addressing the child's difficulties and related psychosocial concerns. Regrettably, this patient population evidences high rates of attrition (e.g., Botchway et al., 2019a & 2019b; Crichton et al., 2018a). Such findings suggest that practitioners should strive to emphasize psychoeducation as well as the importance of sustained monitoring in certain cases. Additionally, as manifestations of sleep disturbance range widely (e.g., parasomnias, bedtime resistance, shorter sleep duration, fatigue, and difficulties initiating and maintaining sleep), it is recommended that post-TBI clinical evaluation protocols incorporate assessments for a range of sleep disturbances. Moreover, increased surveillance is warranted in cases with greater TBI severity.

Improved guidelines for practitioners should incorporate enhanced focus on the identification of sleep disturbance, both in the acute post-injury phase and up to 20 years thereafter. For example, despite the routine use of the CBCL as a measure for post-TBI sleep

disturbance, it is recommended that further research be conducted assessing the validity of the CBCL in a post-pediatric-TBI population. This is important, as research has found that CBCL scores do not consistently correlate with actigraphy (e.g., Landry-Roy et al., 2017). This finding may indicate that different diagnostic measures assess different features/domains of sleep. It is thus recommended that post-pediatric-TBI assessment of sleep disturbances incorporate multiple measures.

In pediatric populations, it may be of benefit to provide psychoeducation regarding the risk of sleep disturbance following a TBI, with the aim of improving surveillance, given the high incidence and numerous negative consequences thereof and the aforementioned tendency of families not to report sleep difficulties (Hawley, 2003). Such psychoeducation should incorporate methods to make the patients and/or their caregiver(s) more cognizant of sleep disturbances following a TBI and may include reporting symptomatology if it presents; tracking relevant symptomatology across academic, home, and social settings; and, for older adolescents, avoiding driving if feeling fatigued. Moreover, research by Howell and colleagues (2019 & 2016) suggests that the relationship between individual symptom profiles and the time to remission of post-TBI symptoms differs by age, with significant differences evidenced between children (aged seven- to 12-years) and adolescents (13-18 years). Taken together, these findings suggest that age-specific and domain-specific assessment may prove more reliable and valid relative to assessment through global symptom severity scores alone. Furthermore, these findings indicate that symptom differences between age groups appear to be manifest only after at least 21 days post-injury but not after 20 years (Botchway et al., 2019a & 2019b; Crichton et al., 2018a; Howell et al., 2019). This indicates that clinicians ought to pay particular attention to age-group differences in symptom manifestation after the acute post-injury phase, as such differences

seem to emerge over time. As previously mentioned, Lah and co-researchers (2019) examined the efficacy of a CBT model known as CBT-I in a pediatric population following a TBI. They observed clinically significant improvements of fatigue (in 100% of cases) and insomnia (in 75% of cases) after four weeks of a manualized CBT-I treatment delivered individually. This research suggests that CBT-I should be incorporated into post-TBI treatment protocols if the patient evidences such need. Relatedly, this review identified a number of correlates of post-TBI sleep disturbance. For example, Fischer and associates (2018) reported that internalizing problems can predict later development of sleep disturbance in children following a TBI. The identification of such correlates may allow for improved treatment efficacy by addressing such predictor variables in the context of clinical practice.

Regardless of the veritable necessity of incorporating neuroradiological assessment and repeated EEGs in severe and complicated brain injury, routine EEG in minor head injuries should generally be avoided; replaced; or supplemented with the use of MRI, voxel-based morphometry, and careful attention to psychoeducation. Post-pediatric-TBI sleep disturbance has been demonstrated to negatively affect parent-child interactions (Lalonde et al., 2020). Therefore, family therapy, in addition to CBT-I, may prove beneficial in not only promoting sleep hygiene, but also in maintaining and improving such parent-child relations.

In summation, it may be advantageous for clinicians evaluating or treating a child with a TBI to conduct a thorough assessment of relevant risk factors associated with TBI, ranging from injury severity to age. Additionally, the incorporation of parent report in tandem with objective measures of post-TBI symptomatology may prove more useful in guiding decision-making as opposed to employing only one assessment method. For example, in one study, parents identified post-injury symptoms (e.g., sleep disturbance) not captured by the ACE (Suskauer and

colleagues, 2018). Relatedly, Milroy and co-researchers (2008) found that parents and caregivers reported sleep disturbances in their children which were not indicated by child report or by objective measures such as actigraphy post-TBI. Furthermore, some publications evidenced a high level of disagreement between parent and child reports of post-TBI pain and fatigue, each of which is independently associated with sleep disturbance (Botchway et al., 2019a; Fischer et al., 2018). It is recommended that parent report be used as a basis for decision-making in tandem with other assessments of sleep disturbance, as parents and other caregivers may be inadvertently reporting inaccurate or non-representative information (Hawley, 2003). Hence, a battery of assessments should be utilized throughout treatment and follow-up to minimize reporter bias and to address the limitations of the specific instruments employed.

Limitations

The present review of the literature is limited in that 11 of the 18 studies (61%) with some type of control data used an orthopedic/extracranial injury control group. Such extracranial injuries and the consequences thereof may independently result in changes in one's sleep behaviors, thereby conflating the data derived from such studies. For example, Fischer and co-researchers (2018) reported that participants with an extracranial injury experienced marginally greater sleep disturbances than patients with a TBI at six- and 12-months follow-up, despite having fewer sleep disturbances at baseline. Therefore, if the control group being utilized is comprised of children who have an extracranial or orthopedic injury, then the results may be skewed, given the apparent increase in sleep disturbance following non-cranial injuries generally. However, other research did not identify similar elevations in post-injury sleep disturbance among patients with non-cranial injuries (e.g., Beebe et al., 2007). Moreover, just 22% of the studies utilized a typically developing control group, and just one (4%) used a sibling

control group, further obfuscating the results obtained. The incorporation of a sibling control group can be beneficial to minimize confounding environmental factors and family variables, but the siblings of participants may evidence changes in emotional functioning consequent to their sibling's injury (Sambuco et al., 2008). Similarly, the incorporation of a typically developing control group may not control for various confounding variables associated with the injury (e.g., hospitalization, treatment, psychosocial consequences).

Seventy-four percent of the studies reviewed utilized parent report. As aforementioned, parent report may be unreliable, as parents and caregivers may not accurately report sleep disturbances in children relative to objective measures (e.g., actigraphy) and child report (Fischer et al., 2018; Hawley, 2003; Milroy et al., 2008). However, the validity of actigraphy in post-pediatric-TBI assessment has not been conclusively determined (e.g., Meltzer et al., 2012; Sadeh, 2011). Additionally, only 39% of the studies reviewed were published in the USA; the results of studies from other nations may not necessarily be representative of figures within the USA due to myriad factors ranging from disparate demographic variables to differences in incidence and/or surveillance. Furthermore, many of the studies assessed for TBI and sleep disturbance using different methods. Such differences in assessment methodology may lead to an unforeseen skewing of the data, as the various methods of assessment present with differences in reliability and validity (e.g., parent-report versus self-report versus actigraphy). Moreover, the studies greatly differed in their inclusion of a representative sample, with the literature predominantly over-representing White males, further restricting the clinical utility of the data.

Although the total sample size for the studies reviewed was quite high, the sample size of the TBI group was significantly smaller; eight of the 23 reviewed studies had a TBI sample size which was smaller than 50. Despite the fact that 11 (48%) of the reviewed studies included

participants with a moderate or severe TBI, the vast majority of the total TBI sample had a specified diagnosis of mild TBI. In fact, 2995 of the 3507 (85%) TBI participants in these studies suffered only mild TBIs. Just 132 (4%) of the participants had a specified diagnosis of severe TBI. This relative paucity of participants with a moderate or severe TBI may lead to a misinterpretation of the derived data, as smaller sample sizes have a larger standard of error, thereby necessitating differences of greater magnitude to achieve statistical significance. This effectively means that changes in the severe and moderate TBI groups might not be readily identified, even if they are large, because of a failure to surmount the limitations of smaller sample sizes. The preponderance of mild TBI participants within TBI sample sets across studies may simply reflect differences in frequency of occurrence. Nevertheless, this is a limitation, as such great differences in sample size surely affect the results derived therefrom and, hence, the clinical utility of those results.

Future Directions for Research

Despite the high rate of post-TBI sleep disturbance in children, little research has been conducted related to the treatment thereof. Only one such study was identified during the course of this literature review. It was a feasibility study with only five participants (Lah et al., 2019). Further research should aim to evaluate potentially useful treatment methodologies for pediatric sleep disturbance following a TBI. Additionally, fatigue is a common facet of sleep disturbance. Nevertheless, the vast majority of the presently reviewed studies do not disentangle the multidimensional construct of fatigue. Rather, much of the research reviewed assessed fatigue generally, but the contemporary model of fatigue typically conceptualizes it as including a number of distinct domains/typologies. For example, Crichton and colleagues (2018b) assessed differing domains of fatigue, including sleep/rest fatigue, cognitive fatigue, and general fatigue.

Their findings indicated that these different fatigue typologies are predicted by different variables and that they are not absolutely colinear. Such findings are supported by parallel research conducted by Bogdanov and associates (2018), who concluded that the different types of sleep disturbance appear to be correlated with distinct variables. Nevertheless, these aforementioned domains of fatigue were consistently predicted by physical/motor and sleep/mood symptoms 12-months post-injury. Botchway and colleagues (2019a), for example, reported that there was a significant association between anxiety as well as pain with post-injury sleep disturbance, but such an association was not found with regard to depression and post-injury sleep disturbance. Further research into the specific domains of sleep and fatigue is a field ripe for investigation and may serve to guide clinical decision-making by enabling the establishment of soundly founded prognoses and treatment plans.

Crichton and co-researchers (2018a) reported that there was a significantly higher attrition rate among non-White participants in their study. Therefore, future longitudinal studies should incorporate analyses of data to determine the relevant impact of ethnically disparate attrition rates. Remarkably, many of the studies reviewed did not present relevant participant demographics of race or ethnicity (e.g., Bernard et al., 2020; Bogdanov et al., 2018; Botchway et al., 2019a & 2019b; Corti et al., 2019; Iyer et al., 2019; Lah et al., 2019). Other studies did not describe race or ethnicity in detail. For example, Shay and co-researchers (2014) presented just the number and percentage of “nonwhite race” participants without operationalizing the variable of “nonwhite race.” Such nebulous categorizations abound throughout the extant literature. They serve to interfere with a clear interpretation of the data and the applicability thereof to a given patient or population. Consequently, it may well be prudent to ensure that future research clearly

delineates participant race and ethnicity. Botchway and colleagues (2019a & 2019b) also reported disparate rates of attrition, particularly between males and females.

Suskauer and associates (2018) reported that caregivers endorsed post-injury symptomatology not captured by the ACE. Likewise, Milroy and collaborators (2008) found that parents and caregivers reported sleep disturbances in their children which were not evidenced either by child report or by more objective measures such as actigraphy post-TBI. Additionally, Bernard and colleagues (2017) concluded that caregiver reporting is most often completed by female participants (89%). As previously mentioned, there appears to be differences in symptom reporting between individuals of different sexes. Given that over 74% of the reviewed studies utilized some form of caregiver report, this is an important factor to consider, as such differences between male and female reporting patterns across the bulk of the studies reviewed may skew the results and reduce the clinical relevance of the data. Therefore, future research should aim to quantify the validity of assessments (e.g., caregiver reports) and determine significant confounding variables (e.g., whether males or females are underreporting or overreporting symptoms of post-TBI sleep disturbance). Furthermore, future research should aim to assess the validity of actigraphy use in children following a TBI relative to the “gold standard” of sleep assessment, i.e., polysomnography (Sumpter et al., 2013, p. 833). Given the potential confounding variables associated with different control groups (e.g., sibling, typically developing, OI), future researchers ought to investigate the use of such control groups to identify resolutely the most appropriate approach for subsequent investigations.

Importantly, none of the studies identified or presented any data of non-binary, third gender, gender non-conforming or trans individuals. Given, the reported differences between males and females in reports of symptom frequency/severity post-TBI, it may prove fruitful to

investigate such effects among children who fall outside the male-female dichotomy. Notably, many of the reviewed studies used either sex or gender as a variable in analysis (e.g., Lah et al., 2019; Lalonde et al., 2020; Milroy et al., 2008; Suskauer et al., 2018). Future research should delineate data of both the sex and gender of participants to paint a clearer picture for clinical application with gender diverse patients.

Future research should continue to pursue the determination of specific factors associated with sleep disturbance following a pediatric TBI as this might allow for early identification, targeted interventions, and the attainment of valuable prognostic data. Hence, future directions for investigation ought to address age-specific and severity-specific long-term sequelae, affording special attention to pediatric issues including academic capability, social interaction, and familial factors. Such studies should aim to employ large sample sizes in equal proportion across age- and severity-stratified groups in an effort to minimize between-group standard of error differences as such differences serve to diminish the clinical utility of the results derived. Additionally, the time course of post-TBI sleep disturbances is unknown, as few studies have followed pediatric patients for longer than 12 months following a TBI. The relative shortage of research on sleep disturbances following a pediatric TBI is remarkable, given the extant evidence suggesting a strong interrelationship between sleep behavior and daytime functioning.

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